

EDITOInfra

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D 5.2

Engine – Installation Guide

Work Package	<i>WP 5 EDITO-Infra Engine Architecture</i>
Authors	<i>Quentin Gaudel, Jérôme Gasperi. Mercator-Ocean International</i>
Reviewers	<i>Simon Lyobard, Mathis Bertin. Mercator-Ocean International</i>
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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document describes the administration steps to install a brand new EDITO Engine on a Cloud provider

1.2 EDITO deployment on CloudFerro

As described in document D2.4 EDITO-Infra architecture – blueprint, domain, stack and deployment-V2, section 3.5 Deployment, the whole EDITO platform deployment is highly automated on Mercator Ocean’s software forge thanks to a [GitOps](#) approach and the use of automation technology (Terraform) for provisioning resources (virtual machines) and application deployment (platform software).

The procedure to (re)deploy the current official EDITO platform instance, deployed on [CloudFerro](#)/WEkEO Cloud provider, is provided in the [EDITO development Git repository README document](#). It includes a PRODUCTION instance and a STAGING instance, deployed on region WAW3-1, and the respective monitoring instances, deployed on region WAW3-2.

It also provides instructions in case the deployment required some customization, such as a change of domains and subdomains of the platform, or the use of a a different software forge instance.

Section 2 recalls this documentation.

1.3 Requirements for an external premise

Installation on external premises (data centers or cloud providers) is possible if they expose API that are compatible with the actual EDITO GitOps code, i.e OpenStack API (including Magnum, Designate, Swift plugins). Some minor modifications must be done as well, such as virtual machine flavor labels, region labels, image versions, Kubernetes version, etc. In case the OpenStack version is different than the one exposed by CloudFerro, more modification might be needed, but we cannot be exhaustive on it considering the number of possibilities.

2. Deploy the EDITO

This section recalls the content of the [EDITO development Git repository README document](#) regarding the EDITO platform deployment.

The section describes how to deploy or redeploy the EDITO platform (available at <https://dive.edito.eu/>) from scratch, using Mercator Ocean's software forge. Indications are provided in each subsection in case some customizations are requested, such as domains and subdomains, and software forge instance.

In this section:

- The "CloudFerro PRODUCTION project" will refer to an OpenStack project at CloudFerro cloud provider on the WAW3-1 region (configured with Magnum, Designate, and Swift plugins).
- The "CloudFerro STAGING project" will refer to an OpenStack project at CloudFerro cloud provider on the WAW3-1 region (configured with Magnum, Designate, and Swift plugins). It is a replication (in terms of configurations) of the first one, dedicated to the STAGING environment.
- The "CloudFerro MONITORING project" will refer to an OpenStack project at CloudFerro cloud provider on the WAW3-2 region, used for the monitoring of the platform (configured with Designate, and Swift plugins).

2.1 Requirements

2.1.1. Requirements for automated deployment with GitLab

The automated deployments rely on Mercator Ocean's GitLab and Nexus instances, that are already pre-configured.

If you want to automate the deployment elsewhere, you will need instances of those available and to modify Nexus credentials in the 'edito.kdbx' KeePassXC database. You also need to configure at least two GitLab runners:

- a [Docker runner](#) labelled docker
- a [Shell runner](#) labelled shell-docker with cURL, Docker, [Make](#) and KeePassXC installed on it

If you cannot label the runners that way, just update the .gitlab-ci.yml file accordingly.

2.1.2. Requirements for manual deployment using a local environment

You will need [Make](#) and [micromamba](#) available on your UNIX system.

2.1.3. General requirements

You'll need to:

- Have your "CloudFerro PRODUCTION project", "CloudFerro STAGING project", "CloudFerro MONITORING project" set up.
- Clone this repository <https://gitlab.mercator-ocean.fr/internal/edito-infra/edito-infra/>. Send an e-mail to edito-infra-dev@mercator-ocean.eu to request access permissions and the KeePassXC database password. It contains some entries that will be used to deploy the platform. It is organized with some "common" entries (available at the root of the KeePassXC database) and some environment related ones under the "STAGING" and "PRODUCTION".
- Edit the 'edito.kdbx' KeePassXC database available at the root of the project. In this KeePassXC database you must:
- Replace the additional attributes values under the WEKEO_OPENSTACK_ACCESS entry available at the root of the database with the values of your "CloudFerro MONITORING project". To generate them, you'll need to create [Create application & S3 credentials](#)
- Replace the additional attributes values under the OPENSTACK_ACCESS entries, for both STAGING and PRODUCTION folders, with the ones of your "CloudFerro STAGING project" and "CloudFerro PRODUCTION project". To generate them, you'll need to create [Create application & S3 credentials](#) for each environment/project.
- Modify all the other entries (**password and additional attributes**), under "Racine", "Racine/STAGING" and "Racine/PRODUCTION" with the desired values.
- You must also change the URL of each entry that contains one in case you decide to use another domain/subdomain.

- Manually create an external floating IP (for the load balancer behind the cluster) in your "CloudFerro PRODUCTION project" and specify it in the terraform-init.sh file, next to TF_VAR_openstack_load_balancer_ip. Do the same for your staging environment in your "CloudFerro STAGING project" if wanted.
- Manually create an external floating IP (for the monitoring) in your "CloudFerro MONITORING project" and specify it in the terraform-init.sh file, next to TF_VAR_monitoring_ip_address and in the terraform/root-modules/infrastructure-services/external-common/variables.tf file, next to splash_monitoring_ip.
- Own those 3 domain names at your preferred registrar: staging.edito.eu. (staging platform), dive.edito.eu. (production platform) and seabed.edito.eu (monitoring platform) and to create the following DNS records:
- For the PRODUCTION environment:
 - CNAME record for my-ocean.dive.edito.eu to cname.vercel-dns.com (explorer viewer, managed by the Lobelia Earth company)
 - CNAME record for *.dive.edito.eu to dive.edito.eu
 - CNAME record for *.lab.dive.edito.eu to dive.edito.eu
 - A record for dive.edito.eu to the public IP address of the OpenStack load balancer in PRODUCTION
 - A record for monitoring-dive.seabed.edito.eu to the public IP address of the monitoring in PRODUCTION
 - CNAME record for _acme-challenge.dive.edito.eu to dive.edito.eu
 - CNAME record for _acme-challenge.lab.dive.edito.eu to dive.edito.eu
 - NS records for _dns-dive.edito.eu to the different domain names of DNS servers used by your cloud provider where the cluster is running. In our case, CloudFerro, which mean: cloud-dns1.cloudferro.com, cloud-dns2.cloudferro.com, cloud-dns3.cloudferro.com
- For the STAGING environment:
 - There's no my-ocean viewer for the STAGING environment
 - CNAME record for *.staging.edito.eu to staging.edito.eu
 - CNAME record for *.lab.staging.edito.eu to staging.edito.eu
 - A record for staging.edito.eu to the public IP address of the OpenStack load balancer in STAGING
 - A record for monitoring-staging.seabed.edito.eu to the public IP address of the monitoring in STAGING
 - CNAME record for _acme-challenge.staging.edito.eu to staging.edito.eu
 - CNAME record for _acme-challenge.lab.staging.edito.eu to staging.edito.eu
 - NS records for _dns-staging.edito.eu to the different domain names of DNS servers used by your cloud provider where the cluster is running. In our case, CloudFerro, which mean: cloud-dns1.cloudferro.com, cloud-dns2.cloudferro.com, cloud-dns3.cloudferro.com

In case you want to change the domain name of the EDITO platform, you'll need to change the DNS rules accordingly.

2.2 Deployment

Once every requirement has been correctly fulfilled, you should be able to deploy.

2.2.1. Automated deployment

- Push the cloned repository to the GitLab instance (in case you are a different GitLab instance).
- Make sure the following CI/CD variable are set:
 - EDITO_INFRA_ENVIRONMENT to PRODUCTION
 - KEEPASSXC_DATABASE_PASSWORD to the KeePassXC database password
 - TERRAFORM_AUTO_APPROVE_OPTION to -auto-approve
- Trigger the main branch [CI pipeline](#) somehow, graphically, by pushing the branch, or even by API.

2.2.2. Manual deployment using a local environment

From the cloned repository root, run:

- make create-environment to create the Micromamba virtual environment embedding the dependencies
- make deploy-internal-waw3-1 to deploy the platform Once the platform has been successfully deployed for the first time, you'll maybe have to restart the onyxia-api deployment in the Kubernetes cluster because we encountered some issues trying to connect to the datalab.
- make deploy-external-MERCATOR to deploy the monitoring

By default, the "STAGING" environment will be used. But you can set up the EDITO_INFRA_ENVIRONMENT environment variable to PRODUCTION if you want to deploy in the PRODUCTION environment.

2.3 Access the platform

You can now access:

- The production platform at <http://dive.edito.eu/>
- The production monitoring at <http://monitoring-dive.seabed.edito.eu:3000/>
- The staging platform at <http://staging.edito.eu/>
- The staging monitoring at <http://monitoring-staging.seabed.edito.eu:3000/>

Update the domains/subdomains with your custom configurations, if any.